

The Day-in-the-Life Programme (DLP) – A CORD Partnership project

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The [CORD Partnership](#) aims to embed a culture of interdisciplinary open research in criminal justice in Ireland. It brings together researchers, policymakers and practitioners from more than 60 organisations across Ireland’s criminal justice and higher education sectors to achieve this.

CORD partners met for a [design workshop in 2024](#) to co-create and vote on ideas to help embed this culture. One of the top-voted actions was for the CORD Partnership to create a ‘day-in-the-life experience’ for its partners to shadow individuals working in other partner organisations.

The **Day-in-the-Life Programme (DLP)** aims to help researchers, policymakers and practitioners better understand each other’s roles and working environments, and facilitate connection and collaboration across criminal justice and research in Ireland. It involves the coordination of one-day study visits, supported by ‘structured shadowing’ techniques to help embed the learning.

How will visits be coordinated and supported?

The CORD Partnership Chair, Dr Ian Marder, will coordinate the visits by connecting and liaising with visitors and hosts. When a person expresses an interest in a visit, Ian will contact a potential host. If they are amenable to acting as a host in principle, Ian will connect the visitor and host to discuss the structure, content and conditions of the visit and draft the learning agreement.

The coordination process is as follows:

- Hosts and visitors will be invited to participate in a facilitated, online meeting to agree a visit structure, content and conditions, and develop a learning agreement.
- Visitors will undertake a visit with their host, which will last a maximum of one day.
- After a visit the visitor and host will be invited to participate in separate, online meetings with the CORD chair to help them reflect on the visit and embed the learning.
- Participants will be invited to allow the pre-visit planning conversation and the post-visit reflection to be analysed to enable the evaluation of the DLP. This is not a requirement.

Stages of a visit in the Day-in-the-Life Programme

What might a visit entail?

Visitors and hosts participating in the DLP will develop and sign a learning agreement outlining the agreed expectations for the visit, including activities and conditions. Activities will depend on the host's role and the visitor's learning goals to enable learning and accommodate logistical challenges. Visits can include various activities, such as shadowing and observation of activities, discussions with the host(s) and colleagues, tours of buildings, and any other activities as agreed and appropriate. For example, if someone visits a university researcher, their visit might include attending lectures or workshops, meeting colleagues, and discussing research and postgraduate degrees. If someone visits a criminal justice organisation, such as a prison or a community-based organisation, the visit might involve touring buildings, observing practices, meeting colleagues and clients, and other activities as appropriate. An outline of each visit will be agreed in advance to ensure that the host and visitor are aligned in their expectations for the visit and everyone is clear as to the activities the visit is likely to involve.

What form of reciprocity is sought?

Partners who undertake a visit will be invited to join the list of possible hosts for a future visit. A future visitor need not be from the organisation they visited, but the person or organisation they visit should be given priority. Hosting and visiting are voluntary, but we hope that visitors will be willing to host a visit later in the spirit of reciprocity. Visitors are not expected to commit the time or resources of others in their organisation, but may consider hosting a visit personally. When a person expresses interest in hosting, they will be asked to reflect on the type of learning experience they could provide, which will be saved to a list of potential hosts.

How will the programme support participant learning?

DLP participants will attend an online, pre-visit planning conversation between the host, visitor and CORD Chair (approx. one hour) to agree the structure, content and conditions of the visit, and provide an opportunity to reflect on knowledge gaps, expectations and learning goals.

Following each visit, hosts and visitors will be invited to a post-visit conversation to discuss their experience of, and the learning from, the visit. The goal of these conversations is to provide an opportunity for reflection and to help embed their learning. Conversations will take place online or in person (approx. one hour). This idea was drawn from the pedagogical field of 'structured shadowing', which discusses the need to embed learning by facilitating structured reflection.

Will this programme be researched?

Participants will be invited to allow the pre- and post-visit conversations to be recorded for use as data to study the programme. Consenting to the research is voluntary and is not required to participate in the programme. Those who consent to their conversations being used as data will be provided with information sheets and consent forms outlining how the data will be collected, stored, analysed and used. This research has been approved by the Maynooth University Social Science Research Ethics Subcommittee.